

Linear free energy relation in Mn^{II} catalyzed oxidation of some α -amino acids by Ce^{IV} – Kinetics and mechanism

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Abstract : Oxidation of α -amino acids (phenylalanine, glycine, alanine, valine, *nor*-leucine and *iso*-leucine) by Ce^{IV} is catalyzed by Mn^{II} in sulfuric acid-water medium and gave aldehyde. All these reactions are first order with respect to amino acid, oxidant, catalyst and inverse second order with respect to H^+ . Rate increases with increase in $[HSO_4^-]$ at constant $[H^+]$ but decreases with $[H^+]$ at constant $[HSO_4^-]$. Active species in this oxidation suggested is $[Ce(SO_4)]^{2+}$. Mn^{II} is first oxidized to Mn^{III} , which act as oxidant for the substrate. Thermodynamic parameters for rate determining step have been evaluated. Formation of cyclic intermediate and free radical mechanism involving C-C fission have been suggested. Linear Free Energy Relationship is satisfied. Reaction constant $\rho = +1.313$, suggesting involvement of formation of electron-deficient species in the reaction. The reactivity decreased as carbon chain length increased and the observed order is phenylalanine > glycine > alanine > valine > *nor*-leucine > *iso*-leucine.

Keywords : Linear free energy, kinetics, oxidation, amino acids.

Oxidation of biologically important compounds like amino acids can be affected by a large number of oxidants including metal ions. Ce^{IV} is an important and strong oxidizing agent but it does not oxidize amino acids. In presence of metal catalysts like iridium(III)¹, chromium(III)², ruthenium(III)³ and silver(I)⁴ etc. amino acids are oxidized by Ce^{IV} . There seems no report on Mn^{II} catalyzed Ce^{IV} oxidation of α -amino acids. The present study deals with the kinetics and mechanism of Mn^{II} catalyzed oxidation of α -amino acids by Ce^{IV} in aqueous sulfuric acid medium.

Results and discussion

Effect of Ce^{IV} : In the presence of large excess of amino acids (10 folds) over the oxidant, the process is first order with respect to Ce^{IV} in all the amino acids taken for study.

Pseudo first order rate constants were calculated by plotting $\log(a - x)$ versus time. However, the pseudo first order rate constant decreases with the initial $[Ce^{IV}]$ (Table 1). Similar behavior was also reported by a number of workers previously in some oxidation reactions with Ce^{IV} in different mineral acid media³. The reasons put forth by different authors to explain the behavior include formation of inactive dimers or trimers from the

active monomeric forms of Ce^{IV} .

Effect of substrate : The rate of reaction is proportional to the concentration of amino acid taken (Table 2). No kinetic evidence for the formation of any reversible complex between amino acid and Ce^{IV} was indicated. A plot of k_{obs} versus $[AA]$ comes out to be a straight-line passing through origin in all the amino acids. The order in amino acid comes out to be one in all the cases, obtained by $\log k_{obs}$ versus \log [substrate] plot.

Effect of Mn^{II} : The rate increases with increase in $[Mn^{II}]$ (Table 3). A plot of $\log k_{obs}$ versus $\log [Mn^{II}]$ is a straight line with slope nearly one in all the amino acids studied.

Effect of ionic strength : No effect of NO_3^- and ClO_4^- on these reactions was observed. This suggests that ion pair is not involved in rate-determining step. There is no effect of Zn^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Cd^{2+} and Ce^{3+} ions on rate of reactions.

Effect of bisulphate ion : Rate increases with increase in $[HSO_4^-]$ keeping constant $[H^+]$ (Table 4). The order with respect to $[HSO_4^-]$ is one. This indicated that $[Ce(SO_4)]^{2+}$ are the reactive species. This is also supported by the effect of H^+ on the rate of oxidation.

Table 1. Variation of rate with Ce^{IV} concentration

[H₂SO₄] = 1.0 mol dm⁻³, [MnSO₄] = 1 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [amino acid] = 2.5 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³, Temp. = 313 K

10 ³ [Ce ^{IV}] (mol dm ⁻³)	10 ⁶ k _{obs} (s ⁻¹)					
	Glycine	Alanine	Valine	<i>nor</i> -Leucine	<i>iso</i> -Leucine	Phenyl alanine
0.7	41.21	32.65	28.86	25.12	18.14	72.64
1.0	39.98	30.17	26.74	22.58	16.95	70.95
1.5	33.58	22.57	22.58	19.88	14.64	67.17
2.0	28.79	20.49	19.21	16.89	13.12	59.81
2.5	23.98	19.21	17.75	15.35	12.40	51.26
3.0	23.46	18.42	17.24	13.82	12.09	46.28

Table 2. Variation of rate with amino acid concentration

[H₂SO₄] = 1.0 mol dm⁻³, [MnSO₄] = 1.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [Ce^{IV}] = 2.5 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³, Temp. = 313 K

10 ³ [AA] (mol dm ⁻³)	10 ⁶ k _{obs} (s ⁻¹)					
	Glycine	Alanine	Valine	<i>nor</i> -Leucine	<i>iso</i> -Leucine	Phenyl alanine
2.00	17.40	16.71	13.65	13.22	10.35	39.66
2.50	23.98	19.21	17.75	15.35	12.40	51.26
3.00	27.64	27.73	21.75	17.75	14.31	58.85
3.75	31.56	27.98	30.71	19.83	16.16	69.60
5.00	41.97	34.00	35.10	28.15	23.74	85.38
6.25	51.18	47.34	42.22	35.82	34.17	94.68

Table 3. Variation of rate with manganese concentration

[H₂SO₄] = 1.0 mol dm⁻³, [amino acid] = 2.5 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³, [Ce^{IV}] = 2.5 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, Temp. = 313 K

10 ³ [Mn ^{II}] (mol dm ⁻³)	10 ⁶ k _{obs} (s ⁻¹)					
	Glycine	Alanine	Valine	<i>nor</i> -Leucine	<i>iso</i> -Leucine	Phenyl alanine
0.10	3.01	3.04	2.88	2.83	2.85	3.99
0.25	6.89	5.00	5.42	4.29	4.49	10.76
0.50	12.82	11.50	10.24	9.38	7.08	25.59
1.00	23.98	19.21	17.75	15.35	12.40	51.26
2.00	44.46	39.22	32.79	25.59	21.11	86.08
2.50	54.45	53.11	44.46	38.48	25.80	118.44
4.00	79.95	79.82	83.85	53.11	36.73	167.96
5.00	120.22	102.57	93.84	68.74	49.55	251.18

The results are contrary to that observed by Sah, who observed an inhibition effect of HSO₄⁻ on rate of bromide-catalyzed oxidation of D-mannose⁶, cellobiose⁷ and melibiose⁷ with Ce^{IV} in aqueous sulfuric acid solution. They proposed Ce(SO₄)₂ as reactive species.

Effect of H⁺ : For variations of [H⁺] over 1.0–2.4 mol dm⁻³ range at fixed [HSO₄⁻], the composition of [H₂SO₄] + [NaHSO₄] = 2.4 mol dm⁻³ was varied assuming [H⁺] = [HSO₄⁻]. Rate of reaction decreased with

increase in [H⁺] (Table 5). This is contrary to findings of Reddy and Shastri⁸. Slope of plots log k_{obs} versus log [H⁺] is ≈ -2. The inverse order with respect to [H⁺] is two.

Effect of temperature : The rate increased with increase in temperature in the range 308 to 323 K (Table 6). Plot of log k_{obs} versus 1/T is a straight line in all the amino acids. Thermodynamic parameters for the rate-determining step are summarized in Table 7.

Table 4. Variation of rate with [HSO₄⁻] at constant [H⁺]

[H₂SO₄] = 1.0 mol dm⁻³, [amino acid] = 2.5 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³, [MnSO₄] = 1.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³,
[Ce^{IV}] = 2.5 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, Temp. = 313 K

[KHSO ₄] (mol dm ⁻³)	10 ⁶ k _{obs} (s ⁻¹)					
	Glycine	Alanine	Valine	<i>nor</i> -Leucine	<i>iso</i> -Leucine	Phenyl alanine
0.00	23.98	19.21	17.75	15.35	12.40	51.26
1.00	34.61	33.62	28.81	25.63	15.10	88.05
1.20	51.23	51.21	41.61	38.41	25.77	140.08
1.40	85.91	76.81	71.32	56.95	42.85	204.74
1.60	115.25	100.87	85.94	76.85	60.60	259.51
2.00	163.82	140.75	125.11	102.44	88.01	345.45
2.40	239.84	191.82	177.55	153.55	124.05	511.84

Table 5. Variation of rate with [H⁺] at constant [HSO₄⁻]

[Amino acid] = 2.5 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³, [MnSO₄] = 1.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [Ce^{IV}] = 2.5 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, Temp. = 313 K

[H ⁺] (mol dm ⁻³)	10 ⁶ k _{obs} (s ⁻¹)					
	Glycine	Alanine	Valine	<i>nor</i> -Leucine	<i>iso</i> -Leucine	Phenyl alanine
1.00	23.98	19.21	17.75	15.35	12.40	51.26
1.20	16.38	14.07	12.51	10.24	8.80	34.55
1.40	11.52	10.08	8.59	7.68	6.06	25.91
1.60	8.59	7.68	7.13	5.69	4.28	20.47
2.00	5.12	5.12	4.16	3.84	2.57	14.08
2.40	3.46	3.36	2.88	2.56	1.51	8.80

Table 6. Variation of rate with temperature

[H₂SO₄] = 1.0 mol dm⁻³, [amino acid] = 2.5 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³, [MnSO₄] = 1.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³,
[Ce^{IV}] = 2.5 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³

Temp. (K)	10 ⁶ k _{obs} (s ⁻¹)					
	Glycine	Alanine	Valine	<i>nor</i> -Leucine	<i>iso</i> -Leucine	Phenyl alanine
303	11.09	8.56	7.67	6.24	7.95	22.39
308	16.08	13.66	11.37	9.55	7.87	35.82
313	23.98	19.21	17.75	15.35	12.40	51.26
318	35.82	28.15	26.92	24.56	19.20	77.79
323	49.58	41.67	38.91	36.91	29.48	110.03

Increase in rate by increasing catalyst concentration i.e. Mn^{II} is explained by the fact that a complex is formed between Mn^{II} and amino acid (eq. 2). This complex than oxidized by Ce^{IV} active species [Ce(SO₄)₂]²⁺ to give Mn^{III}-amino acid complex which subsequently decomposes in slow step (eq. 4). Increase in H⁺ concentration in reaction decreases rate of reaction. This is due to formation of protonated amino acid that cannot form complex with

Mn^{II} and hence rate decreases. Further rate is also decreased by decrease in concentration of active species [Ce(SO₄)₂]²⁺ on increasing concentration of H⁺ ion (eq. 3). The low energy of activation is due to oxidation of Mn^{II}-amino acid complex to Mn^{III} amino acid complex. The values of thermodynamic parameters (ΔE_a[‡] and ΔS[‡]) in all the cases are practically same as that observed for C-C fission and one electron transfer reaction through a

Table 7. Thermodynamic parameters

Amino acid	pZ $10^{11} \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^{-3}$	ΔE^\ddagger kJ mol^{-1}	ΔS^\ddagger $\text{J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$	ΔG^\ddagger kJ mol^{-1}
Glycine	10.47	62.59 ± 1.9	-48.34 ± 1.6	72.78 ± 2.2
Alanine	10.70	64.85 ± 2.0	-44.14 ± 1.5	78.71 ± 2.3
Valine	10.92	66.53 ± 2.1	-39.91 ± 1.3	79.04 ± 2.4
<i>nor</i> -Leucine	11.79	72.07 ± 2.2	-23.26 ± 0.7	79.38 ± 2.4
<i>iso</i> -Leucine	11.85	73.04 ± 2.2	-22.03 ± 0.7	79.92 ± 2.4

Table 8. Variation of rate with substituents

$[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{amino acid}] = 2.5 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$,
 $[\text{MnSO}_4] = 1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] = 2.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$,
 Temp. = 303 K

Amino acid	σ^*	$10^6 k_{\text{obs}} (\text{s}^{-1})$
Phenyl alanine	0.22	22.39
Glycine	0.00	11.09
Alanine	-0.10	8.56
Valine	-0.13	7.67
<i>nor</i> -Leucine	-0.16	6.24
<i>iso</i> -Leucine	-0.16	7.95

complex between substrate and catalyst. It was pointed out⁹ that if entropy of activation is negative and small, the reaction is slow. Therefore, these oxidations come in slow reactions category. Negative value of entropy also suggests :

- (i) Bimolecular reaction in the rate-determining step.
- (ii) Formation of cyclic intermediate from non-cyclic reactants and the internal rotation in the reactant becomes vibration in activated complex with the loss of energy.

Therefore, overall entropy of activation will be negative and frequency factor reduces. The cyclic complex is formed between catalyst Mn^{II} and substrate, which on oxidation by Ce^{IV} disproportionate via one-electron transfer.

α -Amino acids are likely to behave as α -hydroxy acids and such as C-H fission to be expected in rate determining step. However ΔH values are found to be quite different in these oxidations. In fact hydroxy acids involving C-H rupture¹⁰ have low value of ΔH as compared to the value obtained in oxidation of amino acids by Ce^{IV} besides the amino acids differ from hydroxy acid in their chemical behavior. Under acidic conditions hydroxy acid molecules are undissociated and not protonated at O-H while amino acid exist as protonated (at α -NH₂) molecule. Further the thermodynamic parameters and reaction product favors C-C bond rupture and not

C-H bond. It was therefore not considered. Oxidation of amino acids by pyridinium bromochromates¹¹, quinolinium bromochromate¹² and KMnO₄-MnSO₄ in aqueous sulfuric acid¹³ also gave similar products (aldehyde, CO₂ and NH₄⁺) by C-C fission.

The reactivity decreases as carbon chain length increases in amino acids (Table 8). The observed order of reactivity is phenylalanine > glycine > alanine > valine > *nor*-leucine > *iso*-leucine. Linear Free Energy Relation can be applied to these oxidations. The plot of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ versus σ^* (Taft substituent constant¹⁴ taking -CH₂(NH₂)COOH as functional group) is a straight line ($r^2 = 0.9698$) with slope $\rho = +1.313$, suggesting involvement of formation of electron-deficient species (X) in the reaction. Based on above kinetic data, the following mechanism may be proposed for the oxidation of amino acids :

The over all reaction may be represented as :

The over all reaction is also consistent with the stoichiometry observed under kinetic conditions.

The above mechanism leads to the following rate expression :

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Rate} &= - \frac{d[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]}{dt} \\ &= k[\text{C}_1] \\ &= kK_2[\text{C}][\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)^{2+}] \\ &= \frac{kK_2K[\text{AA}]_t[\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}][\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)^{2+}]}{[\text{H}^+]} \end{aligned}$$

$$[\text{Since } [\text{H}^+] \gg [\text{AA}]_t$$

$$\therefore [\text{AAH}^+] = [\text{AA}]_t$$

$$\text{and } [\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)^{2+}] \cong K \frac{[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]_T[\text{HSO}_4^-]}{[\text{H}^+]}$$

$$= \frac{kK_1K_2 [AA]_t [Mn^{II}][Ce^{IV}]_T [HSO_4^-]}{[H^+]^2}$$

$$= k_{obs} [Ce^{IV}]_T$$

where

$$k_{obs} = \frac{kK_1K_2 [AA]_t [Mn^{II}][HSO_4^-]}{[H^+]^2}$$

This rate law explains all the experimental results.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of analytical grade. Ceric ammonium sulfate solution was prepared in 1 M H₂SO₄. The kinetics of the oxidation was followed by mixing aliquots (5.0 ml) of reaction mixture at suitable intervals of time to a known excess of ferrous ammonium sulfate. Excess of ferrous ammonium sulfate was back-titrated against standard potassium permanganate solution using ferroin as indicator.

First order rate constants (k_{obs}) were calculated graphically by plots of $\log [a - x]$ versus time and checked using linear least-square method. Orders with respect to different reactants (α -amino acids, Ce^{IV}, Mn^{II}, H⁺ and HSO₄⁻ etc.) were determined using Ostwald method.

Product study : Product study was made under kinetic conditions, with an excess of substrate over the oxidant. The products of oxidation were the corresponding aldehydes to amino acids and were identified by their 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone derivatives. Ammonia by Nessler reagent and carbon dioxide by limewater were detected as products of oxidation.

Stoichiometry : Stoichiometry was determined under kinetic conditions. Aldehydes produced were quantified by precipitating as 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazones. The ratio of moles of aldehydes formed and moles of oxidant Ce^{IV} consumed is 1 : 2. Hence the oxidation can be represented by equation :

Detection of free radicals : Stabilizer free acryloni-

sodium hydroxide solution followed by distilled water. In kinetic conditions and nitrogen atmosphere this stabilizer free acrylonitrile was added to detect free radicals in the oxidation study. No milky appearance was observed. It seems, either radicals are not formed or radicals produced react faster with Ce^{IV} than with monomer.

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